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**LEGAL FRAMEWORKS, NATIONAL SECURITY, AND
GOVERNANCE IN THE UKRAINIAN EXPERIENCE**

**11-The Issue of Criminal Liability for
Corruption Crimes in The Context of Legal
Modernization. By Anfisa Serhienko and
others. p. 250.**

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**CENTER FOR LAW AND POLITICAL RESEARCH – DENMARK
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**THE ISSUE OF CRIMINAL LIABILITY FOR
CORRUPTION CRIMES IN THE CONTEXT OF
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ABSTRACT

The article is devoted to the study of the problems of criminal liability for corruption offenses in the context of modern international standards and the search

for ways to improve the efficiency of anti-corruption processes. The purpose of the study is to investigate the factors shaping criminal liability for corruption in the context of the international legal framework. The study is based on a systematic approach which combines the doctrinal analysis of international agreements and European directives with the comparative method to compare anti-corruption mechanisms of different jurisdictions. It is found that the modern international anti-corruption system is formed on the basis of a comprehensive combination of universal and specialized legal instruments. The author establishes that European law creates an extensive system of legal instruments which combines criminal law harmonization with mechanisms for coordinating cross-border anti-corruption measures. It is substantiated that the achievement of the European system is the legislative consolidation of liability of legal entities, comprehensive criminalization of various forms of corruption and the definition of minimum sanctions for the unification of judicial practice. The results of this work can be used to improve national criminal legislation on corruption offenses and to implement international standards in the domestic legal system. The proposed approaches will help to increase the effectiveness of anti-corruption institutions and ensure the inevitability of criminal liability for corruption offenses. A comprehensive analysis of the determinants of criminal liability for corruption offenses is carried out through the prism of integration of universal international standards and European legal principles. The author develops a conceptual understanding of criminal justice in the field of combating corruption as a political and economic necessity that affects international trust and regional security.

Keywords: *corruption, criminal liability, international standards, European law, anti-corruption mechanisms, anti-corruption.*

1- INTRODUCTION

Corruption is a complex socio-legal phenomenon that permeates various spheres of public life and manifests itself at all levels of public administration, from individual malfeasance to large-scale transnational schemes. It not only undermines the effectiveness of state institutions, but also poses serious threats to the rule of law, the stability of democratic regimes and the security of the state. In such circumstances, the issues of combating corruption and ensuring the inevitability of criminal liability for such crimes are becoming increasingly relevant, as criminal law mechanisms are one of the key tools in the system of state response to corruption¹. The problem of criminal liability for corruption offenses is not only the establishment of appropriate legal norms, but also their effective implementation, which requires improving institutional mechanisms, improving the legal framework and ensuring the independence of law enforcement agencies. Despite the existence of international standards and a significant

¹ Duisenbayeva, G., Apakhayev, N., Batyrbay, N., Moldabekova, Z., & Nussubaliyeva, M. (2024). Social determinants of corruption and legal methods of counteracting it in the modern conditions. *Social and Legal Studios*, 7(2), 210–221. <https://doi.org/10.32518/sals2.2024.210>

number of anti-corruption measures, the prevalence of corruption remains high, which indicates the insufficient effectiveness of existing criminal legal means².

Therefore, in today's context, research aimed at finding ways to improve the effectiveness of criminal liability for corruption offenses, including analysis of gaps in legislation, practice of its application and identification of promising areas for improvement, is of high importance. It is a holistic approach, which provides for the harmonization of national criminal legislation with international standards and the formation of effective counteraction mechanisms, that will be able to ensure a real reduction in the level of corruption and create conditions for the sustainable development of the country's society.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Researchers of international and European criminal law Matwijkiw et al.³, Syroid⁴ describe the evolution of corruption crimes – from active and passive bribery to influence peddling, money laundering and fraud with public funds. At the same time, the boundaries between corruption crimes and related encroachments on official activities remain fragmented and uncertain, and the problem of unifying the characteristics of the subject of the crime in the public and private sectors remains unresolved.

Publications by Raof et al.⁵, Wicaksana Prakasa⁶ show that strict, proportionate and dissuasive sanctions combined with confiscation increase reparation and overall prevention, while minimum imprisonment thresholds for “substantial harm/benefit” unify judicial practice in criminal proceedings against corruption. At the same time, there is insufficient research on how to adjust special legal documents, taking into account the emergence of new formats of corrupt actions and deeds, especially at the state level.

² Nashruddien, I. A., Mandiana, S., & Setyabudhi, J. J. (2024). Corporate criminal law liability in corruption crimes based on PERMA RI Number 13 of 2016. *Jurnal Indonesia Sosial Teknologi*, 5(7), 3402–3411. <https://doi.org/10.59141/jist.v5i7.1229>

³ Matwijkiw, A., Matwijkiw, B., Roksandić, S., & Engelhart, M. (2025). Crime and corruption. Serious economic crimes and international criminal law – Shaping a new era of international law and justice [Introduction to Special Issue]. *International Criminal Law Review*, 25(2–3), 199–210. <https://doi.org/10.1163/15718123bja10229>

⁴ Syroid, T. (2024). International anti-corruption standards in the private sphere. *The Journal of V. N. Karazin Kharkiv National University. Series Law*, 37, 214–224. <https://doi.org/10.26565/2075-1834-2024-37-25>

⁵ Raof, N. A., Aziz, N. A. A., Omar, N., & Amin Fahmy, W. L. M. (2024). Unmasking company liability for corruption by associated persons. *Journal of Financial Crime*, 31(5), 1222–1236. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JFC-05-2023-0104>

⁶ Wicaksana Prakasa, S. U. (2024). *Reconceptualizing corruption as an international crime: A review of international law*. *Lampung Journal of International Law*, 6(2), 55–68. <https://doi.org/10.25041/lajil.v6i2.3363>

The discourse on illicit enrichment in Mukhlis et al.⁷ and Nedzinskas and Neverbickaite⁸ shows that criminalization without explanation of the legal sources of significant asset gains is an effective response to the latency of corruption and the gap between real benefits and the ability to prove them by classical means. However, there is an ongoing debate about the compatibility of such rules with the presumption of innocence, the reasonable redistribution of the evidentiary burden and standards of proof for criminal confiscation, and the limits of retroactivity and the retrospective period.

The works of Agbor⁹, Shayakhmetova et al.¹⁰, on specialized institutions (anti-corruption units of the prosecutor's office, specialized courts, supranational offices such as the European Financial Action Authority) show that narrow specialization, autonomous budgeting and standardized investigation methods improve the quality of investigation and subsequent criminal prosecution. At the same time, the authors do not fully demonstrate the optimal format of criminal prosecution and prevention of systemic corruption and its spread in public authorities.

In a number of works by Horder¹¹ and Tychyna¹², which discuss the interaction of criminal law with ethical codes of public service and corporate standards, it is established that codes of conduct, gift restrictions and conflicts of interest become a source of obligations, the violation of which may qualify as a crime or as a prerequisite for criminal confiscation. At the same time, there is still a lack of consistent approaches to incriminating "uncodified" ethical violations, proving intent in conflicts of interest without material benefit, and proportionality of criminal response to "ethical and procedural" torts.

⁷ Mukhlis, F., Rizanizarli, & Purnama, E. (2025). Formulation of liability and criminal policy of justice collaborator of corruption in Indonesia. *Journal of Lifestyle and SDGs Review*, 5(1), e04319. <https://doi.org/10.47172/2965-730X.SDGsReview.v5.n01.pe04319>

⁸ Nedzinskas, E., & Neverbickaite, I. (2024). Criminal liability for corruption crimes in Lithuanian court practice. In *Proceedings of the 11th SWS International Scientific Conference on Social Sciences – ISCSS 2024* (Vol. 11, Issue 1.1). SGEM World Science. <https://doi.org/10.35603/sws.iscss.2024/s02/07>

⁹ Agbor, G. C. (2024). *Corporate criminal liability in bribery and corruption in the United States and the world* (SSRN Scholarly Paper No. 5107805). Social Science Research Network. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.5107805>

¹⁰ Shayakhmetova, Z., Kassimova, M., Idressova, U., Kazbekova, A., & Yergaliyeva, K. (2024). International legal regulation of liability for corruption offences. *Scientific Herald of Uzhhorod University. Series Physics*, 55, 164–171. <https://doi.org/10.54919/physics/55.2024.16nr4>

¹¹ Horder, J. (2025). Corporate criminal liability under the Economic Crime and Corporate Transparency Act 2023. *Legal Studies*, 45(1), 133–148. <https://doi.org/10.1017/lst.2024.46>

¹² Tychyna, D. M. (2025). Genesis of criminal liability of an official of a legal entity for corruption crimes. *Analytical and Comparative Jurisprudence*, 2(3), 482–488. <https://doi.org/10.24144/2788-6018.2025.03.2.77>

Comparative studies of the case law of the European Court of Human Rights, according to the scientific works Bogdanova and Allegrezza¹³, De Paolis¹⁴, Serowaniec¹⁵ focus on the balance between the interests of effective criminal prosecution and fair trial guarantees, concluding that the proper quality of criminalization and confiscation laws is the key to the sustainability of sentences. However, the authors should note that standards for assessing the legality and “foreseeability” of illicit enrichment provisions are often not unified, and there are gaps in practice regarding the admissibility of “indicative” presumptions of origin of assets of public officials and citizens.

Summarizing the current research, the authors can determine that the criminal legal tools in corruption cases are becoming more and more complex, but the key nodes regarding the balance of criminal liability and real extraterritorial effectiveness remain underdeveloped, which requires further comparative research aimed at developing coordinated models of criminal liability capable of ensuring the inevitability of punishment and maximum asset recovery.

The aim of the article is to substantiate the determinants of criminal liability for corruption offenses in the context of modern international standards and European legal principles.

3. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study is based on a systematic approach which combines qualitative analytical methods for an in-depth study of legal issues and ways to improve them. The key tool is a doctrinal (legal) analysis, which includes a study of the legal system, including international agreements, European directives and domestic legislation. This approach helps to identify shortcomings in the criminalization of corruption, such as illicit enrichment or conflict of interest, and allows to assess their impact on the rule of law. The comparative method was used to compare the anti-corruption mechanisms of the EU, the UN and the Council of Europe with the experience of the participating countries. Its use helped to identify best practices, such as the formation of specialized institutions (in accordance with GRECO recommendations) or systems for the seizure of illicit assets. The retrospective method is used to track the development of legal provisions from the 2009 Lisbon Treaty to current resolutions, which demonstrates the directions of criminal law unification.

¹³ Bogdanova, I., & Allegrezza, S. (2025). *EU sanctions implementation and enforcement: Legal and policy recommendations*. KLEPTOTRACE. https://www.kleptotrace.com/wp-content/uploads/2025/03/Final-Report_Legal-and-Policy-Recommendations-February-2025.pdf

¹⁴ De Paolis, R. (2025). Corruption, sextortion, genderbased violence: Open challenges for the European Union in harmonising substantive criminal rules. *New Journal of European Criminal Law*, 16(1), 3–30. <https://doi.org/10.1177/20322844241293634>

¹⁵ Serowaniec, M. (2025). The protection of EU financial interests in Poland: Administrative and criminal critical issues. *European Papers*, 9(3), 1198–1215. https://www.europeanpapers.eu/en/system/files/pdf_version/EP_eJ_2024_3_SS2_7_Maciej_Serowaniec_00805.pdf

4. RESULTS

4.1. INTERNATIONAL AND EUROPEAN LEGAL FRAMEWORK OF CRIMINAL LIABILITY FOR CORRUPTION OFFENSES

The modern legal discourse undoubtedly outlines the fact that combating corruption is not only the work of internal state measures, but also the widespread use of international standards that have been developed by the international community over several decades. As Lykhova et al.¹⁶ rightly note, the legal mechanism for combating corruption largely depends on the international norms and principles enshrined in universal and regional legal acts and documents. One of the fundamental legal documents aimed at the global formation of a unified approach to combating and prosecuting corruption was the 1996 United Nations Declaration on Combating Corruption and Bribery in International Business Transactions¹⁷. Paragraphs 5-7 of this act recommends that countries around the world develop and apply accounting and financial reporting standards that would ensure transparency of commercial transactions and prevent the possibility of hidden bribery or financial fraud.

The authors should also highlight the Lima Declaration on Financial Control, which defines the principle of transparency and accountability of governments at all levels of government¹⁸. The document explicitly states that public accounts should be open to public scrutiny, and the public should have real access to information on the use of budgetary resources. The authors believe that these provisions create a direct link between financial control and criminal liability, since the establishment of a system of public declarations of income and property of officials actually forms the evidence base for future criminal proceedings in cases of unjustified enrichment. Thus, although they are not legally binding, declarations serve as a kind of political and legal guidelines, and they set the vector for national legislators and create an ideological basis for strengthening criminal liability for corruption¹⁹.

The conventions of international and regional organizations are binding on the member states and have the greatest impact on the development of criminal law in the

¹⁶ Lykhova, S. Y., Lysko, T. D., Kosilova, O. I., Kyrychenko, O. V., & Shamara, O. V. (2022). Criminal liability for corruption offenses: A comparative legal aspect. *Informatologia*, 55(1–2), 76–97. <https://doi.org/10.32914/i.55.1-2.7>

¹⁷ United Nations General Assembly. (1996a). *UN Declaration against Corruption and Bribery in International Commercial Transactions*, A/RES/51/191, U.N. Doc. A/51/49 (Vol. I). <https://www.refworld.org/legal/resolution/unga/2013/en/95718>

¹⁸ International Organization of Supreme Audit Institutions. (1977). *The Lima Declaration of Guidelines on Auditing Precepts* [INTOSAIP 1]. International Standards of Supreme Audit Institutions. <https://www.issai.org/pronouncements/intosai-p-1-the-lima-declaration/>

¹⁹ United Nations General Assembly. (1997). *Action against corruption* (Resolution A/RES/51/59). <https://www.refworld.org/legal/resolution/unga/1997/en/10513>

field of combating corruption. The most comprehensive document in this area is the UN Convention against Corruption (20, ratified by more than 180 countries. It contains not only preventive mechanisms, but also clear provisions on criminalization of bribery, illicit enrichment, abuse of power, and money laundering. Particularly noteworthy are Articles 7-9 of the Convention, which regulate transparency in the public service and public procurement. The authors note the fact that the Convention provides for the obligation of States Parties to introduce systems for declaring the income and expenses of officials, as well as mechanisms for their verification²⁰. These features are directly related to the effectiveness of criminal prosecution: only the availability of reliable data on the assets of officials allows law enforcement agencies to prove the fact of illicit enrichment.

The Inter-American Convention Against Corruption²¹ and the African Union Convention²² also contain provisions on the need to criminalize illicit enrichment. The materials of the above documents demonstrate the existence of a global consensus: without recognizing illicit enrichment as a crime, the fight against corruption loses its effectiveness. The authors propose to implement into national legislation not only criminal liability for illicit enrichment, but also procedural mechanisms for special confiscation of property that does not correspond to official income. It is also worth emphasizing the importance of the Council of Europe's Civil and Criminal Conventions²³, which complement the EU's universal standards by providing for the liability of not only individuals but also legal entities for corruption crimes. These documents emphasize the need to impose sanctions against companies, including liquidation or prohibition to participate in public procurement²⁴.

Codified "soft law" acts such as the International Code of Conduct for Public Officials²⁵ or the Code of Conduct for Law Enforcement Officials²⁶ have a preventive

²⁰ United Nations. (2003). *United Nations Convention Against Corruption*. United Nations Treaty Series, Vol. 2349, p. 41. <https://www.unodc.org/documents/treaties/Special/2003%20United%20Nations%20Convention%20Against%20Corruption.pdf>

²¹ Organization of American States. (1996). *InterAmerican Convention Against Corruption (B58)*. Adopted at the Specialized Conference on the Draft InterAmerican Convention Against Corruption; entered into force March 6, 1997. https://www.oas.org/en/sla/dil/inter_american_treaties_B-58_against_Corruption.asp

²² African Union. (2003). *African Union Convention on Preventing and Combating Corruption*. Adopted at the 2nd Ordinary Session of the Assembly of the African Union in Maputo, entered into force August 5, 2006. <https://www.refworld.org/legal/agreements/au/2003/en/63979>

²³ Council of Europe. (1999). *Criminal Law Convention on Corruption (ETS No. 173) and Civil Law Convention on Corruption (ETS No. 174)*. Council of Europe.

²⁴ European Parliament, Council of the European Union, & European Commission. (1999). *Interinstitutional Agreement between the European Parliament, the Council of the European Union and the Commission of the European Communities concerning internal investigations by the European AntiFraud Office (OLAF)*, OJ L 136, 31/05/1999, pp. 15-19. https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/agree_interinsttit/1999/531/oj

²⁵ United Nations General Assembly. (1996b). *International Code of Conduct for Public Officials (Annex to A/RES/51/59)*. United Nations. <https://hrlibrary.umn.edu/resolutions/51/59GA1996.html>

function. They not only ensure the formation of ethical standards, but also create the basis for legislative detailing of crimes related to violation of the rules of ethics²⁷. For example, the asset declaration requirements, the prohibition on accepting gifts or benefits defined in these codes can be directly implemented into national criminal law as grounds for direct criminal liability.

Anti-corruption resolutions of the UN and the Council of Europe, although not binding, serve as a catalyst for national reforms. For example, the 1990 UN General Assembly Resolution “Practical Measures to Combat Corruption” emphasizes the need to create electronic declaration systems. And the 1997 Resolution of the Committee of Ministers of the Council of Europe No. 97/24 “On Twenty Principles for Combating Corruption” directly requires the confiscation of illegally obtained income, the creation of specialized anti-corruption bodies and transparency of public procurement (Table 1)²⁸.

Table 1. Assessment of international legal instruments of criminal liability for corruption offenses

Instrument	Description	Legal basis	Assessment of effectiveness	Suggestions for improvement
1. Criminalization of active and passive corruption	Establishment of criminal liability for bribery and abuse	Protocol of 1996 to the 1995 Convention, Directive (EU) 2017/1371	High: ensures inevitability of punishment, preventive effect	Extension to indirect forms, increased sanctions for legal entities
2. Liability of legal entities	Fines, liquidation, confiscation of assets for corruption	Second Protocol of 1997, OECD Convention of 1997	Medium: effective against commercial entities, but depends on national implementation	Unification of confiscation standards, international recognition of sentences
3. Specialized investigations (OLAF)	Internal audits and control over EU finances	Inter-institutional agreement of 1999	High: promotes transparency, detects fraud	Integration with national prosecutor's offices, expansion of

²⁶ United Nations General Assembly. (1979). *Code of Conduct for Law Enforcement Officials (A/RES/34/169)*. United Nations. <https://www.ohchr.org/sites/default/files/codeofconduct.pdf>

²⁷ United Nations General Assembly. (1979). *Id.*

²⁸ Council of Europe Committee of Ministers. (1997). *Resolution (97) 24 on the Twenty Guiding Principles for the Fight against Corruption*. [https://www.coe.int/t/dghl/monitoring/greco/documents/Resolution\(97\)24_EN.pdf](https://www.coe.int/t/dghl/monitoring/greco/documents/Resolution(97)24_EN.pdf)

				powers
4. Confiscation of corrupt assets	Seizure of bribes and proceeds, recovery of funds	1997 Convention, 1999 Council of Europe Criminal Convention	High: makes legalization impossible, restores justice	Automation of processes, strengthening of international cooperation
5. Recommendations on party financing	Transparency of contributions, sanctions for violations	Recommendation Rec(2003)4 of the Committee of Ministers of the Council of Europe	Medium: sets standards, but not binding	Transformation into mandatory norms, criminalization of violations

Source: compiled by the authors

These provisions are of direct relevance to criminal law: they outline the range of acts that should be recognized as criminal offenses and identify key areas for improving the sanctioning mechanism. In our opinion, the implementation of the principles of the resolutions into national law will strengthen both the preventive and punitive functions of criminal justice. The EU Public Procurement Directives (2014/23/EU, 2014/24/EU, 2014/25/EU) are an example of combining digital technologies and legal mechanisms in the fight against corruption. They regulate the conduct of electronic auctions, the creation of open electronic catalogs, and the mandatory publication of information on all types of procurement by the state/state agencies.

4. 2. CRIMINAL LIABILITY FOR CORRUPTION OFFENSES IN THE SYSTEM OF MODERN EUROPEAN LAW

A study of the experience of the European Union and international institutions in the field of combating corruption shows that criminal law mechanisms play a key role in the formation of a system of checks and balances that effectively ensures strict adherence to the rule of law and protection of the financial interests of both nation states and supranational associations. A historically important stage in this process was the reform enshrined in the Lisbon Treaty, which entered into force on December 1, 2009, and which significantly changed the system of interaction between member states in the criminal law area. It was this treaty that eliminated the so-called “three pillars” system inherent in the Maastricht Treaty and at the same time integrated the provisions of the former Article 31 into the new Article 83 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union. The fundamental changes defined a new architecture of EU criminal law, including the fight against corruption crimes, and enshrined the rulemaking

procedure in this area in Article 294, which indicated the expansion of the Union's competence in lawmaking and an attempt to create a more coherent legal system²⁹.

The authors emphasize the fact that there is still heterogeneity in EU criminal law, as it does not exist in the form of a single unified code, but consists of several interrelated blocks. In particular, there is the administrative and criminal law of the Union; rules relating to substantive criminal law and procedure that impose obligations on national systems; the EU criminal procedure law itself; and project developments on the creation of a single European criminal law (Corpus Juris). In our opinion, these processes indicate the formation of a relatively independent criminal legal system with its own normative, institutional, and empirical components, and thus European integration in this area has long gone beyond the purely declarative level.

At the same time, authors emphasize that the integration of the criminal legal systems of the Member States does not imply their complete unification. The authors can confidently speak of gradual harmonization and coordination, not centralization of criminal justice. In other words, states retain their national criminal legal systems, but in certain areas, such as the protection of the Union's financial interests or the prevention of corruption, they are obliged to adapt their legislation to common standards. This kind of process can be considered optimal, since it helps to avoid a number of conflicts in the field of legal traditions, but at the same time it contributes to the formation of a single European legal space, in which criminal liability for corruption offenses is inevitable and unified in terms of basic parameters³⁰.

A special place in the formation of standards of criminal liability for corruption is occupied by regulations aimed at protecting the financial interests of the EU. The 1996 Protocol to the 1995 Convention stipulated the need to criminalize both passive and active corruption and to establish sanctions proportionate to the gravity of the act. The Second Protocol of 1997 went further, enshrining the provisions on the liability of legal entities, which was an important step, since it is through commercial structures that the proceeds of corruption are often laundered³¹. The sanctions provided for - from deprivation of the right to state aid to the liquidation of legal entities - are not only punitive but also preventive.

The 1999 inter-institutional agreement on internal investigations of the European Anti-Fraud Office (OLAF), which established tools to ensure transparency and control within the Union, made a significant and tangible contribution to the development of anti-corruption practice. Directive (EU) 2017/1371 was a new step, establishing a transparent list of criminal offenses that harm the EU's financial interests, including

²⁹ Duisenbayeva, G., Apakhayev, N., Batyrbay, N., Moldabekova, Z., & Nussubaliyeva, M. (2024). *Id.*

³⁰ Council of Europe Committee of Ministers. (2003). *Recommendation Rec(2003)4 to member states on common rules against corruption in the funding of political parties and electoral campaigns.* <https://rm.coe.int/16806cc1f1>

³¹ Nashruddien, I. A., Mandiana, S., & Setyabudhi, J. J. (2024). *Id.*

fraud, money laundering, active and passive corruption, and misuse of funds³². The authors believe that this directive has become an important milestone in the formation of a unified European approach, as it was the first to comprehensively enshrine the obligation of member states to criminalize a wide range of corrupt practices with clear guidelines for minimum sanctions.

The authors also emphasize the Corpus Juris 2000 document, which proposes to criminalize not only active and passive forms of corruption, but also conspiracy, aiding and abetting. This approach demonstrates the EU's desire to narrow the space for impunity as much as possible and ensure that all accomplices in criminal activity are brought to justice. It is quite logical that provides for quite severe sanctions: 5 to 7 years of imprisonment for individuals and multimillion-dollar fines for legal entities, supplemented by measures such as publication of the verdict or exclusion from the system of state subsidies. In the author's opinion, it is the severity and inevitability of sanctions that create real preventive mechanisms, because without fear of punishment, even the best norms remain declarative³³.

The content of the 1997 Convention on the Fight against Corruption, which applies to officials of the European Communities and its Member States, clearly defines the concepts of "official" and "corruption", establishes criminal liability not only for the acts themselves, but also for complicity, incitement, and conspiracy. These legal principles confirm the thesis that a comprehensive format for criminalizing corruption practices has been crystallized. In this regard, the authors emphasize the legal contribution of the Council of Europe, namely, the Criminal Convention on Corruption established an extremely broad list of acts, including abuse of influence, corruption in the private sector, among judges, and in international organizations. It provides for not only criminal liability of individuals and legal entities, but also the possibility of confiscation of property, and expanded provisions on jurisdiction and international cooperation. The Additional Protocol of 2003 clarified these provisions by extending them to arbitrators and jurors. The Council of Europe Civil Convention³⁴ for the first time at the level of international law defined the universal concept of "corruption" and established mechanisms for compensation for damage caused by corrupt acts. The author believes that the combination of criminal and civil remedies is the most effective, as it allows not only to punish the perpetrators but also to restore the violated rights of the victims (Figure 1).

The well-known case law of the European Court of Human Rights is also noteworthy, as it is a source of law for member states and forms standards for interpreting corruption through the prism of human rights. The ECHR emphasizes that the fight against corruption cannot be carried out at the expense of violating

³² European Parliament & Council of the European Union. (2017). *Directive (EU) 2017/1371 on the fight against fraud to the Union's financial interests by means of criminal law* (OJ L 198/29–41). <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dir/2017/1371/oj>

³³ European Commission. (2000). *Corpus Juris 2000 (Florence Proposal): Follow-up feasibility study of the Corpus Juris on criminal law protection of the EU's financial interests. European Public Prosecutor's Office background*. <https://www.eppo.europa.eu/cs/souvislosti>

³⁴ Council of Europe. (1999). *Civil Law Convention on Corruption (ETS No. 174)*. Council of Europe. <https://rm.coe.int/168007f3f6>

fundamental rights, and therefore, criminal prosecution must be combined with compliance with procedural guarantees. At the same time, the peculiarity of European anti-corruption law is that the basic documents of the Council of Europe are simultaneously implemented in the national legal systems of all EU member states, which achieves a double effect through harmonization of approaches within the European Union and their integration into the wider European space³⁵.

Such facts have already become the basis for asserting that anti-corruption norms do not function as isolated legal instruments, but as a comprehensive system that is binding on the participants and becomes a benchmark for the candidate countries.

It should also be added that the EU adopts both general documents aimed at combating crime, such as Council Decisions 2002/584 or 2001/500, and specialized acts directly related to corruption. One of the key examples is the 1997 Bribery Convention, which defines the obligations of state parties to criminalize active and passive corruption, and provides for the establishment of measures for the seizure and confiscation of bribes and proceeds of corruption³⁶. The authors believe that the obligation of states to take procedural measures to confiscate corrupt assets is one of the most effective tools, as it makes it impossible to legalize criminal proceeds and creates the preconditions for restoring justice in public finance.

Another basic type of legal acts in the field of corruption prevention is international recommendations adopted at the level of the Council of Europe, covering a wide range of issues, from financing political parties and election campaigns to the development of e-democracy. Documents such as the 2003 Recommendation of the Committee of Ministers of the Council of Europe on common rules for combating corruption in the field of political party financing, the Recommendation on e-Democracy³⁷, the Recommendation on Judges: Independence, Efficiency and Duties³⁸,

³⁵ Zazzaro, F. (2025). Corporate criminal liability in EU Directives: An overview of the EU discipline. *New Journal of European Criminal Law*, 16(2), 197–212. <https://doi.org/10.1177/20322844251338625>

³⁶ Makedon, V. V., Valikov, V. P., & Koshlyak, E. E. (2020). The global labor market in the coordinates of the digital economy. *Academic Review*, 52(1), 91–107. <https://doi.org/10.32342/2074-5354-2020-1-52-9>

³⁷ Council of Europe. (2009). Recommendation CM/Rec(2009)1 of the Committee of Ministers to member states on electronic democracy (e-democracy). Council of Europe. <https://rm.coe.int/16805d3bc3>

are not legally binding, but their impact is to formulate soft law standards that reflect best practices and become a reference point for states seeking to improve their own anti-corruption systems³⁹.

Figure 1. Organizational and public principles of the EU anti-corruption strategy development

³⁸ Council of Europe. (2010). Recommendation CM/Rec(2010)12 of the Committee of Ministers to member states on judges: independence, efficiency and responsibilities. Council of Europe. <https://rm.coe.int/16807096c1>

³⁹ Ochnio, A. H. (2024). Recent developments in EU anticorruption strategy: The missing element of the return of corrupt assets to “victim countries”. *Journal of Money Laundering Control*, 27(7), 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JMLC-11-2023-0176>

Source: compiled by the authors

Recommendation emphasizes the need for a unified approach to the regulation of political party and election campaign financing. The document emphasizes transparency of financial flows, limiting external influence, controlling expenditures and imposing sanctions for violations of the rules established. Article 16 of this Recommendation requires states to establish effective, proportionate and preventive sanctions that would apply to both political parties (up to the loss of state funding or the obligation to reimburse contributions received) and individual political figures (up to the revocation of a mandate or temporary prohibition to hold certain positions)⁴⁰. The authors believe that these norms should be viewed not only as advisory, but also as model provisions that can form the basis for improving national criminal legislation in terms of strengthening liability for violations of political finance rules.

4. 3. CRIMINAL LIABILITY FOR CORRUPTION OFFENSES AS A DETERMINANT OF SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT AND AN INSTRUMENT OF MODERN GEOPOLITICS

There is a clear trend in international law: the fight against corruption is not limited to purely criminal prosecution, but is being integrated into the broader context of global sustainable development, security and human rights policy. The authors see that the criminalization of corruption should be accompanied by the development of institutional guarantees of integrity and accountability. The European Union, in particular, emphasizes that there can be no compromise on the rule of law and the fight against corruption, as these factors determine the credibility of political systems and economic stability in the region.

The authors should also not ignore the fact that the consequences of corruption go far beyond the borders of a single state and are truly transnational in nature, as they create the preconditions for the development of organized crime, terrorism, capital outflow, undermining investment attractiveness and increasing social inequality. Therefore, criminal liability for corruption offenses should be not only an element of national legislation, but also a part of international obligations that provide for cooperation in extradition, mutual recognition of sentences, confiscation of assets and joint investigations⁴¹.

The authors can state that there are several key areas for improving criminal liability. First, it is necessary to introduce more detailed corpus delicti of corruption-related crimes, such as illicit enrichment, indirect forms of bribery, abuse of influence or conflict of interest, which are still often overlooked in law enforcement practice. Secondly, it is important to develop specialized anti-corruption prosecutor's offices and courts capable of handling complex cases without political influence, in line with the

⁴⁰ Council of Europe Committee of Ministers. (2003). *Id.*

⁴¹ Makedon, V. V., Kholod, O. H., & Yarmolenko, L. I. (2023). The model for assessing the competitiveness of hightech enterprises on the basis of the formation of key competences. *Academic Review*, 2(59), 75–89. <https://doi.org/10.32342/2074535420232595>

recommendations of GRECO and the European Commission. Thirdly, it is advisable to strengthen international cooperation in terms of information exchange, joint investigation and recovery of illegally withdrawn assets, in line with the provisions of the UN Convention against Corruption⁴².

Legal efforts should be focused on the inevitability of punishment, which should be a key principle of criminal policy. When a significant number of corruption crimes go unpunished due to loopholes in legislation, political compromises or a low level of evidence, society loses confidence in the very idea of the rule of law. Therefore, the task of legislators is to create a mechanism where prosecution does not depend on the social status or political weight of the person. The experience of EU countries demonstrates that only systematic use of criminal prosecution of high-ranking officials creates public confidence in the reality and fairness of anti-corruption policy⁴³.

The European Commission clearly recognizes the complexity and multifaceted nature of this phenomenon and focuses its work on several strategic areas. First, it is the systematic integration of anti-corruption provisions into all areas of EU legislation, which allows for a so-called horizontal approach, when the fight against corruption is not limited to criminal prosecution but extends to economic, social, educational and environmental policies⁴⁴. Secondly, an important area is monitoring and evaluation of the state of anti-corruption at the level of member states, which is implemented through regular reports, reports and statistical analyzes that identify both strengths and weaknesses of national anti-corruption strategies. Thirdly, attention is also focused on the processes of providing technical assistance, financial resources and opportunities for exchange of experience, which helps to strengthen the institutional capacity of EU member states and candidates for accession.

The authors emphasize that regular EU reports not only state the actual state of affairs, but also form a kind of trust rating, as the European Union countries traditionally occupy leading positions in the world in the Corruption Perceptions Index. According to the 2024 data, ten of the twenty least corrupt countries belong to the EU, which confirms the effectiveness of the common policy, but also demonstrates the uneven results: some countries are “leaders” in anti-corruption activities, while others remain “outsiders”, which poses a threat to the stability of the entire Union⁴⁵. In our opinion, harmonization of criminal law and ensuring common standards for the

⁴² Nguyen, K. V. (2024). *Confronting transnational corporate crimes: Urgent global measures. Access to Justice in Eastern Europe*, 7(4), 421–446. <https://doi.org/10.33327/AJEE-18-7.4-a000106>

⁴³ Bogdanova, I., & Allegranza, S. (2025). *Id.*

⁴⁴ Pajak, K., Omelyanenko, V., Makedon, V., Shevchenko, V., Ovcharenko, I. (2020). *Raising the level of financial security of the enterprise based on the basic risks differentiation. Journal of Security and Sustainability Issues*, 10(1), 115-130. [https://doi.org/10.9770/jssi.2020.10.1\(9\)](https://doi.org/10.9770/jssi.2020.10.1(9)).

⁴⁵ De Paolis, R. (2025). *Id.*

prosecution of corruption offenses is the way to equalize such imbalances and further contribute to reducing internal gaps between Member States (Figure 2)⁴⁶.

The authors note that corruption destroys not only the economic foundation of democratic states, but also directly affects the legitimacy of government, creating parallel illegal systems that undermine the rule of law. It is the doctrine of the rule of law, which is one of the fundamental principles of European Union law, that suffers the most from the spread of corrupt practices, as they undermine trust in the judiciary, hinder the realization of human rights and create inequality in access to resources. The principles of transparency, accountability and integrity, which are defined as the three main pillars of anti-corruption policy, also have a role to play.

Figure 2. Measures of systemic counteraction to corruption at the state level
 Source: compiled by the authors

They serve as clear guarantees that the state authorities not only criminalize corrupt acts, but also create conditions in which they become unlikely to occur. If these

⁴⁶ European Partners against Corruption / European Anti-Corruption Network. (2025). *Best anticorruption practices in Europe (BACPE): Legal and policy recommendations*. https://www.kleptotrace.com/wp-content/uploads/2025/03/Final-Report_Legal-and-Policy-Recommendations-February-2025.pdf

principles are ignored, a systemic inequality of access to resources, services and opportunities arises, undermining justice in society and provoking new manifestations of crime⁴⁷. It can be suggested to supplement the criminal liability system with preventive measures aimed at creating an environment of integrity: these can include strict rules for declaring the income and property of officials, as well as the creation of mechanisms for public control over the finances of political parties, public procurement or the activities of the judiciary (Table 2).

Table 2. Ways to improve and develop international law to strengthen liability for corruption offenses

Way of improvement	Format of implementation	International standards	Expected result
Detailing of corpus delicti	Introduction of detailed definitions for all forms of corruption, including indirect bribery and conflict of interest	UN Convention against Corruption 2003, Council of Europe Criminal Convention 1999	Reduction of loopholes in legislation, more effective prosecution
Establishment of specialized bodies	Establishment of independent anti-corruption prosecutor's offices and courts	GRECO recommendations, EU directives on the rule of law	Increase the independence of investigations, reduce political influence
Strengthening international cooperation	Development of mechanisms for data exchange, joint investigations and extradition	UN Convention against Corruption, EU regulations on asset confiscation	Fight against transnational corruption, recovery of stolen funds
Ensuring the inevitability of punishment	Establishing mechanisms independent of the status of the person	UN Sustainable Development Goals, experience of EU countries	Increasing public trust, prevention of corrupt practices
Integration of preventive measures	Introduction of declaration and public control	EU transparency principles, monitoring by the	Creating an environment of integrity,

⁴⁷ Serowaniec, M. (2025). *Id.*

		European Commission	reducing social inequality
Monitoring and evaluation of effectiveness	Regular reports and indicators to assess anti-corruption strategies	Corruption Perceptions Index, European Commission reports	Harmonization of standards, equalization of imbalances between countries

Source: compiled by the authors

It is obvious that the joint fight against corruption within the European Union is not only necessary, but also has no alternative. It promotes the rule of law, the protection of human rights and freedoms, the development of democratic institutions, and creates the preconditions for sustainable economic growth and partnerships in the business sector. In addition, coordination of efforts in the fight against corruption reduces the level of organized crime, strengthens international security and creates conditions for maintaining social harmony among countries.

5-DISCUSSION

The scientific results obtained show that the current system of criminal liability for corruption offenses is actively being formed under the influence of international and European regulatory standards. Although this process is accompanied by some progress, it also raises a number of debatable issues when the findings are generally consistent with the studies of Duisenbayeva et al.⁴⁸ and Nashruddien et al.⁴⁹, which emphasize the importance of strengthening criminal legal mechanisms in the fight against corruption. However, the scientific conclusion about the low effectiveness of criminal liability in cases of illicit enrichment and conflict of interest partially contradicts the views of Wicaksana Prakasa⁵⁰, who considers the criminalization of such acts to be a universal solution, even in the absence of additional procedural guarantees.

The state of liability of legal entities for corruption crimes remains controversial. Horder⁵¹ and Zazzaro⁵² argue for the need to harmonize approaches to corporate responsibility, our study shows that there are still no uniform mechanisms for applying sanctions at the national level, which leads to significant differences in their effectiveness. These findings point to the fact that the problem lies not only in the

⁴⁸ Duisenbayeva, G., Apakhayev, N., Batyrbay, N., Moldabekova, Z., & Nussubaliyeva, M. (2024). *Id.*

⁴⁹ Nashruddien, I. A., Mandiana, S., & Setyabudhi, J. J. (2024). *Id.*

⁵⁰ Wicaksana Prakasa, S. U. (2024). *Id.*

⁵¹ Horder, J. (2025). *Id.*

⁵² Zazzaro, F. (2025). *Id.*

imperfection of legal norms, but also in the lack of unified procedures for criminal prosecution of legal entities.

A special feature of the study was a systematic comparative analysis of international and European legal acts with a focus on their practical implementation in national legal systems. This approach made it possible to identify specific legal gaps and internal contradictions. In particular, it has been confirmed that the effectiveness of criminal liability directly depends on a combination of repressive and preventive measures, as well as on the functioning of independent anti-corruption bodies. These positions are consistent with the conclusions of Mukhlis et al.⁵³ and Serowaniec⁵⁴, but are supplemented by taking into account the geopolitical context of anti-corruption policy making.

Thus, the study offers the scientific community a reasonable position: criminal liability for corruption should be considered not just as a punishment tool, but as an integral part of a comprehensive strategy for sustainable development that covers economic, social and security areas.

CONCLUSION

6.

It is found that the modern international anti-corruption system is formed on the basis of a comprehensive combination of universal and specialized legal instruments which create both regulatory and institutional prerequisites for establishing criminal liability for corruption offenses, with universal instruments, in particular the United Nations Convention against Corruption of 2003, functioning as a basic guideline for the formation of national mechanisms for criminal prosecution of corruption. The author assesses how international standards are gradually forming a single global space for criminal law response to corruption challenges, but their practical effectiveness critically depends on the depth and quality of national implementation, ensuring the principle of non-selectivity in law enforcement and guaranteeing the inevitability of punishment for corruption offenses.

It is found that European law creates a comprehensive and extensive system of legal instruments which effectively combines elements of criminal law harmonization between Member States with mechanisms for coordinating cross-border anti-corruption measures. It is substantiated that the achievement of the European system of criminal liability is the legislative consolidation of liability of legal entities for corruption offenses, comprehensive criminalization of various forms and manifestations of corruption, and also the definition of minimum sanctions which ensure unification and uniformity of judicial practice among the Member States of the European Union.

It is determined that the immediate practical effectiveness of criminal law measures to combat corruption critically depends on the optimal combination of punitive and preventive mechanisms, including the creation of specialized anti-

⁵³ Mukhlis, F., Rizanizarli, & Purnama, E. (2025). *Id.*

⁵⁴ Serowaniec, M. (2025). *Id.*

corruption bodies with expanded powers, the introduction of mandatory detailed financial reporting for public officials, ensuring maximum transparency of public procurement procedures, and the development of effective mechanisms of public control over the activities of the authorities. The author has developed a conceptual understanding that improving the criminal justice system in the field of combating corruption is not only a purely legal, but also a critical political and economic necessity that directly affects the level of confidence of international investors, the legitimacy of government in the eyes of citizens, and the security of international relations.

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